

Cognitive Adaptation Motivation Program (CAMP): A Pilot Study in Enhancing the Psychological Resilience among Adolescents in the Coastal Area of Kerala, India

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Adolescents in coastal Kerala are regularly exposed to environmental dangers and psychological stressors that negatively impact their psychological resilience and mental health. Therefore, applying interventions during calamities is crucial. This study aims to develop, and pilot test a program developed to enhance the psychological resilience of adolescents living in the coastal areas of Kerala, India. Conklin's developmental model was used to develop the intervention program. The Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC-25), focus groups, and interviews were used to identify the main issues. The developed Cognitive Adaptation Motivation Program (CAMP), which integrates cognitive, adaptive, and motivational theories, was implemented over six weeks at a rate of 60 minutes per session to the 10 participants. Results of the single-group pilot experiment showed a significant difference in the pre- and post-test scores of the participants. Adolescents in Kerala, India's coastal region, demonstrated significant enhancement after participating in the CAMP program.

Keywords: Adolescents, psychological resilience, cognitive processing, adaptive motivation, coastal region of Kerala

Adolescence is a time of significant developmental transformation (Morris et al., 2021). Adolescents manage fiercely competitive workplaces while juggling demands from families, schools, and society. These factors may interfere with psychological and physical development, raising the risk of mental health problems in this age range (Yu & Liu, 2025). The mechanisms by which resilience qualities predict or enrich psychological discomfort are still little understood, despite the fact that half of all adolescents encounter mental health concerns at some point in their lives (Ballard et al., 2023).

Adverse childhood experiences, parental mental health problems, bullying behaviours, and serious threats are all known risk factors for the development of psychiatric illnesses in children and adolescents, according to earlier studies (Mesman et al., 2021). Adolescence is a crucial period when mental health issues are common (Zhu et al., 2024). Adolescents' emotional difficulties are impaired by social and physiological factors (Yu & Liu, 2025). To get the best possible outcomes for mental health, psychological resilience is essential (Akdağ et al., 2024). The potential influence on adolescents' mental health is more severe the more risk factors they come across (World Health Organization, 2025).

Adolescents' psychological, educational, social, and emotional

well-being can be greatly improved by insights from resilience research. Psychological enhancements help not only the present functions of an adolescent but also the future (Shean, 2015). Resilience is the ability to overcome challenging situations (Olsson et al., 2003). The word "resilience" comes from the Latin "resiliens," which refers to a material's ability to change with its surroundings and revert to its beginning state (Ye et al., 2023). One who has resilience skills handles major challenges while maintaining stability and growth (Anderson & Priebe, 2021). Resilience uses protective and vulnerable elements while dealing with life challenges effectively (Zukerman et al., 2024). The ability to successfully adapt in the face of adversity, trauma, tragedy, threats, or significant stressors is how the American Psychological Association defines it (American Psychological Association, 2023).

In a variety of settings, natural disasters are a major cause of psychological suffering for adolescents (Anil et al., 2020). These tragedies result in a variety of physical consequences, including mortality, infections, and injuries, as well as economic consequences. The unfavourable effects frequently have major harmful effects on social and psychological functioning (Joy et al., 2021). The impact on mental health can be influenced by a person's level of resilience as well as by a number of demographic factors (Rahana et al., 2021). Earthquakes and tsunamis are instances of severe events that can cause psychological injury to survivors, like trauma, sadness, and anxiety (Lomeli-Rodriguez et al., 2025). The psychological trauma appears to be higher when individuals experience repeated natural disasters (Joy et al., 2021). Different disaster incidents in India have indicated that survivors show symptoms of anxiety and depression. These individuals also show diminished functioning in psychological and physical aspects (Rahana et al., 2021). Adverse conditions can contribute to psychological dysfunction and to behaviors that represent maladaptive responses (Hu et al., 2024). A study that was conducted in the United Kingdom revealed that emotional distress was

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considerably elevated in individuals affected by floods. This study indicated that a substantial percentage of individuals in the sample satisfied diagnostic criteria for anxiety (24.5%), for stress following trauma (27.9%), and for depression (35.1%) (Joy et al., 2021).

Kerala, in the southwestern part of India, shows patterns of disasters that occur in the area, and these disasters produce effects on individuals in the population (Mohan et al., 2020). Individuals who experience situations that involve difficulty or that produce memories of difficult events show reduced ability to manage responses to disasters and to develop recovery from these events (Panigrahi & Suar, 2020). Studies indicate that approaches that do not provide focus on mental health following disasters produce problems that continue over time, and these problems affect individuals and also affect the ability of the community to develop unity and to show recovery (Mohan et al., 2020). Adolescents in the population who experience disasters that occur multiple times show responses that include memories of previous events and feelings of sadness and also show fear relating to disasters that may occur in the future (Philip & Vithya, 2022).

The program was developed to address these challenges. CAMP provides an approach that combines principles from theory examining thinking processes and theory examining motivation for change. This approach addresses thinking factors, emotional factors, and motivation factors that relate to outcomes. The theory examining thinking processes indicates that reinterpretation of difficult experiences occurs through changes in thinking patterns (Resick & Schnicke, 1992). The theory examining motivation for change shows that motivation following from purpose and beliefs in personal capacity provides means for managing stress (Nurmi, 1991). The design of the program follows the model from Conklin (1997) that includes planning, design, implementation, and assessment. The approach combines these elements to develop regulation of emotions, methods for managing stress, and motivation in adolescents. This provides means for these individuals to manage difficulty with increased flexibility in thinking.

Recent findings show the importance of providing organized programs that relate to context for adolescents who experience challenges from the environment and from social factors. Studies indicate that adolescents who experience disasters show increased distress in psychological functioning, increased anxiety, and decreased adaptive functioning (Lomeli-Rodriguez et al., 2025; Rahana et al., 2021; Philip & Vithya, 2022). Analysis examining multiple studies suggests that most programs that provide resilience approaches are temporary or do not include a framework from theory, and this limits the value in settings with limited resources and high risk (Chmitorz et al., 2018; Llistosella et al., 2023; Schäfer et al., 2024). Elements involving thinking processes and motivation, such as regulation of individual responses, orientation toward goals, and adaptive patterns of thinking, show significant effects in developing psychological resilience (Surzykiewicz et al., 2022; Yu & Liu, 2025; Hu et al., 2024). The development of the Cognitive Adaptation Motivation Program (CAMP) responds to this gap. It combines approaches that change thinking patterns and approaches that develop motivation into a program that relates to culture and provides direct interaction for adolescents in coastal regions of Kerala, India, who experience disasters.

Method

Participants

The study selected ten individuals aged eleven to seventeen years for

initial examination from areas along the coast in Kerala, India. These individuals who had not participated in similar work provided agreement for participation and were selected using specific inclusion criteria that included the following: (a) age between eleven and seventeen years, (b) location in coastal areas of Kerala, (c) experience with challenges from the environment and social factors such as flooding or moving from the original location, (d) participation in school or programs in the community, and (e) measures showing low to moderate capacity for response to challenges using the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC-25).

Research Design

The study used the approach that Conklin (1997) provided for developing programs. This approach included four main phases: planning, design, implementation, and evaluation. Franz et al. (2015) indicate that using the approach from Conklin improved the relevance of programs and allowed resources to focus on the most important current needs for large groups. The first phase involves planning. The first phase of the study involved planning, which entailed identifying program goals, conducting a needs assessment, setting program objectives, identifying target audiences, writing program objectives from the extensive study of the existing related literature, and analyzing data gathered from surveys, interviews, and focus group discussions involving the target populations. The second phase involved the design and implementation of the CAMP Intervention Program. This phase included selecting and developing what the program should present, selecting or developing the means for providing the program and the materials that supported it, and developing the timeline that showed when implementation should occur. The third phase of the study involved evaluating and validating the efficacy of the CAMP intervention program in targeting low psychological resilience among the selected adolescents living in the coastal area of Kerala, India.

The study examined individuals in schools and followed procedures that required approval from the authority. Data collection occurred in these schools after this initial step. We selected a total of 211 participants from the five schools. These adolescents were selected with the help of schoolteachers, social workers and youth coordinators working with the coastal families. From this pool, ten participants were selected who met the criteria for the pilot study.

Ethical Consideration

This pilot experimental study was conducted considering the ethical issues, and permission was gained from the Ethical Review Committee of the University of Santo Tomas, Manila, Philippines. The research obtained informed consent from the adolescents and from the parents or guardians to participate in this study. Individuals in the study received information that they have the right to leave the program at any time without any condition.

The researcher, before conducting the research, established that individuals participating in the work were given safe and supportive conditions. All sessions that provided occurred in places that individuals with authority in the school or in the community approved, and these places provided private conditions and maintained information as private. Individuals received information about the proper means to use materials, and all information that identifies these individuals remains private in a strict manner. The study provided debriefing to participants after each session and

provided access to support relating to guidance if this support appears necessary.

Measures

Demographic Information Form. The DIF was used to obtain the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants, including age, gender, and grade. Questions were also included to determine whether individuals had been exposed to stressors such as flooding, displacement, or instability in economic conditions. This form helped confirm that individuals met the criteria for the study and were adolescents residing in the coastal area of Kerala.

The CD-RISC-25 was used to measure resilience among individuals in the study. It is an instrument with twenty-five items designed to assess the ability to cope with stress and adversity. Each item is rated on a scale with five points ranging from zero, indicating not true at all, to four, indicating true nearly all the time, with higher scores indicating greater resilience. The scale measures aspects such as competence in personal factors, acceptance of change, control, and influence of spiritual factors. The CD-RISC-25 has been validated across different populations and demonstrates good consistency in internal measures, with a value of .92.

Cognitive Adaptation Motivation Program (CAMP) Intervention Program: The following procedure was used in the program design. First, the theoretical concepts and therapeutic techniques of the Cognitive and Adaptation Motivation therapies were skilfully integrated into the modules of the program. Second, the extracted themes from the discussions and interactions with the adolescents who have low psychological resilience and apply them to the needs of the adolescents living in the coastal areas were collected. Third, goals were developed from the different sections of the collected data. Fourth, a complete CAMP handbook with the program's objectives, key ideas, and particular exercises was developed. These program sessions for adolescents aimed to enhance psychological resilience, living in disaster-prone coastal communities, addressing their cognitive, emotional, social, and motivational functioning

Cognitive Adaptation Motivation Program (CAMP) Modules and Objectives: The first module was focused on enhancing relationships among participants. During group planning, this method created a background that facilitated learning. According to research on group techniques, building comfort and trust among participants early on has a significant impact on involvement (Edmondson & Lei, 2021). People have the chance to share personal information as part of the study. In an activity planned to foster comfort among members, participants shared their backgrounds and lifestyles. Previous studies reveal that building trust among the participants can help the group to feel less fearful (Forsyth, 2020; Wilson et al., 2022). After this first exercise, there was a group planning, and in the group planning, a summary of the CAMP interventions was given, and this summary included objectives, structure and the expected result of the program. According to the study, if the participants are given the information in the beginning about the program in a detailed way helps them to be motivated and prepared (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2021). If a group develops guidelines together, it will help the members to have a good, safe and encouraging atmosphere for learning, and they also start sharing because they know that this is a confidential platform, and they also develop mutual respect by listening to each other (Julien, 2023). This method of building relationships, giving program information in the beginning and as a group developing the norms helped them to have

their confidence level increased. According to research, trust among the group members is a very important factor for learning as a group (Rogers & Farson, 1957/2021). Hence, the first phase provided a foundation for the growth of the program (Wentzel, 2023).

The second module provided an examination of approaches for managing stress and responses, among adolescents, as they often come across these kinds of experiences (Modecki et al., 2017). Individuals in the study participate in activities that allow identifying factors producing stress. These factors, including demands from school, relationships with others, and conditions in family settings, are the main sources of stress in adolescents (Zimmer-Gembeck et al., 2023). Participants develop the means to separate approaches that provide positive outcomes from approaches that produce negative outcomes. Finding assistance from people, employing techniques to focus attention, and participating in physically demanding activities are examples of positive strategies. Negative strategies include routines of avoiding circumstances or abusing drugs (Moeller et al., 2020). Activities that allow interaction, such as creating visual representations of stress, provide means for individuals to show factors producing stress and responses that relate to these factors, and this process increases awareness of responses (Gross & Uusberg, 2024). The activity using physical demonstration allows individuals to show and remember different approaches for managing stress. This activity increased retention through direct engagement (Immordino-Yang & Damasio, 2007). Activities involving situations that require responses position individuals in conditions where they practice managing stress using positive approaches. This method shows effects in improving regulation of responses and patterns of functioning that allow positive outcomes (Ahern et al., 2008). Through these activities, individuals developed an understanding of managing stress as a process that continues and changes over time. They develop the means to identify sources of stress, use approaches that provide positive outcomes, and develop awareness of responses and the means to manage difficult conditions in regular experiences (Bondarchuk et al., 2024).

The third Module examined motivation and discipline relating to the development of resilience (Martin, 2002). Individuals in the study participate in activities that involve reflection to establish objectives for themselves. These objectives provide a basis for motivation (Murray, 2022). Participants identify motivators that occur within the individual, such as values that the person maintains, and motivators that occur outside the individual, including relationships that provide support. Activities that involve direct participation include developing circles that show motivation for making these sources visible to observation. Individuals also develop boards that show vision to present aspirations and steps that allow action. The module includes challenges with structure relating to focus that provide teaching for techniques of maintaining attention when distractions occur (Jurkowski et al., 2024). These activities allowed participants to develop an understanding of motivation. They also allowed improvement of discipline in the individual and a sense of purpose and meaning. This approach also developed a community that provides support.

The fourth module aimed at changing negative thought patterns that could stop personal growth and emotional health. Participants were encouraged to recognise negative self-talk and cognitive biases like black-and-white thinking and exaggeration, alongside established negative beliefs that prevent effective coping strategies

(Ezawa & Hollon, 2023). These patterns also include beliefs that limit the use of approaches for addressing difficulties. The study uses a method that follows three stages. This method allows individuals to stop thoughts that occur without control, to change focus toward different perspectives, and to use statements that provide support (Ezawa & Hollon, 2023). Activities that develop mental locations enable participants to examine responses in contexts that do not include evaluation (Andrew et al., 2023). Other activities connect thoughts with emotional responses. These activities support understanding of relationships between internal processes and allow greater awareness of patterns (Gross & Uusberg, 2024). The main focus involves developing capacity to examine thoughts that do not support outcomes and to increase dialogue that provides benefits (Ezawa & Hollon, 2023). When participants change thoughts from forms that limit function to forms that reflect actual conditions and support action, results show increases in confidence. These changes also improve regulation of emotional responses in ways that allow flexible responses to conditions (Bonanno et al., 2024; Kalisch et al., 2024). The changes contributed to overall strength in responding to difficulty and to general well-being.

The fifth module concentrated on promoting social adaptation among the adolescents and helped them to build healthy relationships. A friendship recipe Card and social circle mapping tasks were given to the participants to help them improve their friendships and develop a clear picture of their social networks, which would enable them to understand the worth and quality of their relationships (García-Moya et al., 2022). To improve participants' skills of empathy, assertiveness and prosocial behaviour, role play activities that focused on common struggles like rejection, conflict and miscommunication were given. All throughout the training period, the importance was given to empathy, cooperation, and respect for each other, which would help them to cultivate healthy relationships. Towards the end of this module, participants gained a deeper understanding of the importance of supportive friendships and improved their social communication skills, which helped them to feel that they belong to the community and are connected to each other (Allen et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2024).

The sixth module provided support for personal development and confidence, taking into consideration the previous findings. In order to improve motivation and support in all areas of life, the participants were given activities that helped them to assess their growth and to identify their strengths, and it will help them to think in a positive way towards their future (Bates-Krakoff et al., 2022). Another activity called the confidence ladder was used to understand their

achievements and what hinders them from reaching their goals. This helped them to monitor their progress, and this important progress helped them to have confidence in themselves. The next exercise was the best future self-exercise. The intention behind this activity was to give them a chance to think and speak about what they want to do in the future. This can bring about optimism and meaningful behaviour, and they will also learn to deal with challenges (Meevissen et al., 2011). In addition to this, they were given organised self-assessment, and it helped them to identify their goals and the areas that are to be improved and helped to manage situations healthily by themselves and encouraged them to adapt to challenging situations (Mendoza & Yan, 2025). The above-mentioned group activities helped the participants to improve their confidence and become aware and prepared for their future personal development. When strong support was given for future-oriented thinking, participants showed significant motivations and goals and empowerment actions (Messman et al., 2022). The main aim was to help them understand themselves and make concrete changes to make their lives meaningful and purposeful, and this supported an empowered approach towards a meaningful direction (Colla et al., 2022).

Expert Evaluation

The CAMP Intervention Program was evaluated by a panel of six mental health professionals. The panel followed evaluation guidelines that provide a modified form of the USAID instrument. The examination that the panel conducted indicated strong support for the program. Each individual on the panel provided an A rating for the program following the assessment. This rating suggests that the CAMP Intervention program shows features that appear sound and relevant, and that the program appears possible to use in practice. The program showed consistency and reliability when the panel examined the program using measures of agreement between different individuals rating the program. The measure of agreement between individuals was found to be 0.79. The support that the panel provided indicates that the program appears trustworthy and that the program shows a high degree of likelihood of producing positive outcomes when the program is used.

A pilot study examined whether the program could be used in practice. Ten children who showed low psychological resilience were chosen. In this pilot study, a one-group pre-test and post-test design was used. The analysis used the Wilcoxon signed-rank test to examine differences between measures taken pre-test and post-test because the sample included a small number of participants. The study used the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC-25) to measure the efficacy of the CAMP program.

Table 1
Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test Results Before and After the Treatment

Variable	Pre-test	Post-test	Z	p
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)		
Resilience	32.00(4.98)	71.50 (3.89)	-2.814b**	.005
Hardiness	13.00 (2.86)	20.00(1.82)	-2.814b**	.005
Coping	8.10(2.72)	12.20(1.75)	-2.820b**	.005
Flexibility	5.30 (1.63)	10.30(1.15)	-2.820b**	.005
Purpose	8.30 (1.57)	12.60(1.35)	-2.821b**	.005
Optimism	3.50(1.35)	5.90(.737)	-2.827b**	.005
Emotion regulation	1.40(1.42)	5.80(.788)	-2.820b**	.005
Self-Efficacy	3.90(.737)	6.10(.567)	-2.842b**	.004

Notes. N=10, p=0.05 level of significance; **-based on positive ranks

Results

Table 1 reveals that there was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the participants on all dimensions of psychological resilience, as indicated by the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test. The post-test mean scores were consistently higher than the pre-test scores across all variables, showing substantial improvement after the treatment.

Resilience increased notably from the pre-test ($M = 32.00$, $SD = 4.98$) to the post-test ($M = 71.50$, $SD = 3.89$), with a significant Z value of 2.814 ($p = .005$). Similar improvements were seen in hardiness (Pre-test: $M = 13.00$, $SD = 2.86$; Post-test: $M = 20.00$, $SD = 1.82$, $Z = 2.814$, $p = .005$) and coping (Pre-test: $M = 8.10$, $SD = 2.72$; Post-test: $M = 12.20$, $SD = 1.75$, $Z = 2.820$, $p = .005$). Flexibility also increased substantially from the pre-test ($M = 5.30$, $SD = 1.63$) to the post-test ($M = 10.30$, $SD = 1.15$), with a significant Z value of 2.820 ($p = .005$).

Purpose scores improved from the pre-test ($M = 8.30$ ($SD = 1.57$)) to post-test to ($M = 12.60$ ($SD = 1.35$)) with significant Z value of 2.821, $p = .005$), while optimism increased from $M = 3.50$ ($SD = 1.35$) to $M = 5.90$ ($SD = .737$), with a significant Z value of 2.827 ($p = .005$). Emotion regulation scores also showed a large improvement (Pre-test: $M = 1.40$, $SD = 1.42$; Post-test: $M = 5.80$, $SD = .788$, $Z = 2.820$, $p = .005$). Finally, self-efficacy increased significantly from the pre-test ($M = 3.90$, $SD = .737$) to the post-test ($M = 6.10$, $SD = .567$), with a Z value of 2.842 ($p = .004$).

Since all p -values were below the .05 level of significance, the results clearly indicate that the treatment produced significant positive changes in all aspects of psychological resilience among the participants.

Therefore, the results reveal that the six-week intervention program caused a statistically significant change in the level of psychological resilience of adolescents, indicating that CAMP positively affected the participants to enhance their psychological resilience. The pilot study results were consistent with the expert validation, attesting that the CAMP enhanced the psychological resilience of adolescents from the coastal area.

Discussion

This study provided the result that the Cognitive Adaptation Motivation Program significantly improved resilience among adolescents in coastal areas of Kerala that are prone to disasters and other social exploitations. The statistically significant enhancements in all dimensions of resilience, which include hardiness, coping, flexibility, purpose, optimism, emotional regulation, and self-efficacy, implied that a structured, theory-driven intervention can enhance adolescents' adaptive capabilities in high-risk settings (Bonanno et al., 2024; Schäfer et al., 2024). The results revealed that adolescents with high-risk environments can enhance their adaptive abilities through an organised strategy based on theory. The Cognitive Adaptation Motivation Program's success demonstrates how important it is to apply the theory of thought processing with the theory of motivation for adaptation (Kalisch et al., 2024; Yu & Liu, 2025). The above-mentioned elements work together to help participants address unhealthy thoughts, regulate emotions, and develop a sense of motivation and purpose among adolescents that helps them to increase their resilience.

In this program, six modules were included, and with the help of

these six modules, participants attained several skills; they were able to become aware of their stressful situations, and in that situations what constructive coping mechanisms should be used, if there is negative thought arises how to reframe them and how to connect with the peer group and join goal oriented activities. The development of these skills is important among adolescents who face flooding, displacement, and social exploitation. Adolescents in these areas are vulnerable to difficulties such as anxiety, depression, and helplessness. The improvements observed in this study among the adolescents in the program were consistent with research from other settings (Surzykiewicz et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2024). This study showed that the CAMP intervention program based on cognitive and motivational theories can reduce distress and improve adaptive skills among adolescents who face unexpected challenges. The experts who evaluated the program also suggested that the Cognitive Adaptation Motivation Program is appropriate for adolescents. It is relevant to the culture and feasible to implement in coastal communities that have limited resources.

Implications and Limitations of the Study

The positive outcomes of this pilot study highlighted significant implications for practices related to adolescent mental health, education, and community-oriented care. The CAMP can be included in Schools, NGOs, and disaster relief teams' programs to enhance the psychological resilience of the adolescents living in the coastal areas of Kerala, India. The structure of CAMP, which used separate components in sequence, allowed it to work in programs that develop skills in schools and in programs for adolescents. Teachers and individuals who provide guidance, and individuals who work in the community can use this approach to improve how adolescents manage difficulty, how they control emotional responses, and how they maintain engagement with goals. The focus of the program on the connection between individuals, on understanding the position of other individuals, and on support between individuals in the same group may also develop networks in the community that reduce effects of stress from the environment and from social conditions. CAMP provides a model that develops resilience as a measure that prevents difficulty rather than as a response following difficulty, and this model may support emotional competency over time, involvement in academic work, and mental health.

The CAMP intervention program has a few limitations, too. First, this endeavor is only a pilot study. The full efficacy of the intervention program can be determined by implementing it using a true experimental design. Secondly, the participants were only ten adolescents as a result, the findings cannot be generalised. To optimise the benefits of the CAMP intervention program, it should be evaluated on a wider group of people with a more comprehensive preparation and across cultures.

Conclusion

The findings from this pilot study show that the Cognitive Adaptation Motivation Program presents an approach that uses a theory-based intervention that can enhance the psychological resilience of adolescents in coastal Kerala, India, who experience disaster conditions and social exploitation. The program combines methods that work with thinking patterns, methods that increase motivation, and methods that develop skills relating to emotions and

social interaction. This combination produces effects on abilities that allow adaptation, including abilities for managing difficulty, abilities for regulating emotions, and beliefs about the capacity to perform. In describing the overall implications, the program provides a framework that offers practical application and that reflects appropriate features for the cultural context, and this framework supports and increases psychological resilience among adolescents living in the coastal area of Kerala, India.

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